

LIQUID PROCESSABLE, THERMALLY STABLE, HYDROPHOBIC, PHENOLIC-TRIAZINE RESINS FOR ADVANCED COMPOSITE APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Composite structures are seeing demand for higher temperature performance and thus there is a need for advanced resin systems to meet this requirement. Here a commercial phenolic-triazine (PT) resin is combined with a blend of low viscosity difunctional cyanate ester (Primaset™ LECy) to achieve a series of reactive binary systems. Throughout this work, the properties of the blends are compared against an industrial standard (Primaset™ PT-30). The thermomechanical performances of the cured blends compare favourably with the industrial standard system with the best performing systems exhibiting T_g values in excess of 300 °C, based on the drop in storage modulus (compared with a value of at least 350 °C for PT-30). After conditioning for 3127 hours at 80 °C and 85% RH, a cured binary resin blend absorbed 4.9 wt% of moisture, compared with a figure of 5.2 wt% for PT-30. When exposed to 250 °C in air continuously over a period of 3048 hours, the best performing of the binary cured blends lose 48.3 % of their mass, compared with 45.0 % for PT-30 under the same conditions. The importance of this work is that the newly proposed resin blends containing 20 to 25 wt% LECy exhibit low viscosities (<1000 mPa.s) at 50 °C and are considerably more suitable for liquid composite moulding processes when compared with the state-of-the-art commercial matrix, while showing improved moisture performance, with only minimal loss in thermal performance.

1 INTRODUCTION

Advanced carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) composites offer unparalleled specific strength and stiffness when compared with metallic components [1], but care must be exercised when selecting the polymers to fulfil the role of organic matrices in the engineering materials. When designing complex, high performance aerospace components produced from CFRP, the demands of the application are of paramount importance and where high thermal stability and mechanical strength are key requirements, thermoset polymer matrices are commonly used [2]. At the more modest operating

temperatures experienced in secondary applications in civil aviation (*i.e.* with continuous service conditions up to 121 °C/250 °F with short duration spikes up to 204 °C/400 °F), epoxy/CFRP components produced from di- and tri-functional epoxy monomers are perfectly capable of prolonged service life, when cured with aromatic polyamines. Tetrafunctional epoxy resins [3] are also available, which extend the ceiling temperature further by offering higher glass transition temperatures, but as advanced composites are increasingly considered for more demanding environments, then conventional difunctional epoxy resins are no longer considered adequate.

As ceiling temperatures rise, the choice of organic matrices becomes more limited [4] to the use of highly aromatic polymers, such as linear polyimides bearing reactive end caps [5] (*e.g.* PMR 15 [6] and its commercial successor DMBZ-15 which incorporates 2,2'-dimethylbenzidine [7], and PETI 330 [8]), or phenol-formaldehyde resins (phenolic novolacs) [9] and closely related phenyl aralkyl resins, and epoxy novolacs [10]. While a variety of other polymers have been offered [11] (*e.g.* bismaleimides [12,13], and most recently polybenzoxazines [14]), these have either proven to be more limited in terms of thermo-mechanical properties, thermo-oxidative stability, or have simply yet to achieve wider adoption in the more conservative industrial sectors, such as civil aerospace.

Of the more recent commercial offerings, phenolic-triazine (PT) resins, based on oligomers of cyanated novolacs, have become increasingly adopted where applications demand high glass transition temperatures (T_g) coupled with thermal stability [15]. Consequently, they are being considered in the production of CFRP components for gas turbine propulsion units, although their organic nature limits their (extended) use in air in more thermally critical areas to operating temperatures below 250 °C. PT resins are typically processed in prepreg form (pre-impregnated carbon tape) as their comparatively high viscosity (296 Pa.s at 72 °C) renders it impractical to process them in liquid form without the introduction of solvents, which might lead to porosity, void formation during the curing process, and the potential to accelerate depolymerisation in the cured network [16].

The aim of the present work is to combine a commercial PT oligomer with a second liquid cyanate ester monomer with the intention of producing liquid processable systems that are stable at room temperature, display increased thermal reactivity, while maintaining or improving upon the ultimate properties of the cured materials.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Materials

Primaset™ PT-30, an oligomeric phenolic cyanate (average value of $n = 1$), (**1**) and Primaset™ LECy (**2**) were purchased from Lonza AG (Visp, Switzerland) and were used as received (Table 1).

Chemical Name	Trade name	Number	Structure
Phenolic triazine oligomer	Primaset™ PT-30	1	
1,1-bis(4-cyanatophenyl)ethane	Primaset™ LECy	2	

Table 1: The chemical structures of the monomers used in this work

For clarity, each monomer is assigned a number, by which it will be referred throughout this work. In the case of blends, the notation [1_x:2_y] is used, where 1 and 2 are the assigned monomer numbers and x and y are their corresponding weight percentages in the blend composition.

2.2 Formulation and curing of PT resins

The binary blends were prepared by weighing 1 and 2 into a 100 ml reaction vessel (coated three times with Frekote 700-NC *ex* Loctite) in the desired ratios (ranging from 100:0 to 75:25 by weight) and stirred by hand at 125 °C for 2 minutes. The resulting homogeneous blends were poured into the desired mould, in which they were degassed for 20 minutes at 125 °C in a vacuum oven. Resin samples were cured in a convection oven using the following cure cycle, unless otherwise stated: 160 °C for 1 hour, 200 °C for 3 hours, and 250 °C for 1 hour. Owing to its viscosity, prior to weighing, Primaset™ PT-30 (1) was heated to 90 °C for 30 minutes.

2.3 Rheological analysis

Rheology measurements were performed using a TA Discovery HR-1 hybrid rheometer instrument equipped with a parallel plate fixture. Disposable aluminium plates of 25 mm in diameter with a gap of 0.5 mm were used. To determine whether the shear rate influences the viscosity of the blends tested, a flow sweep test was performed at 35 °C with shear rate of 0.1 – 100.0 s⁻¹. This was followed by a temperature ramp program. Samples were heated from room temperature to 130 °C (well below their gel point), at a heating rate of 5 Kmin⁻¹. The strain frequency used was 1 Hz and an oscillation amplitude of 50 % was selected, as this fell well within the linear viscoelastic regime.

2.4 Thermo-oxidative stability

Cured samples of each material (0.0150 ± 0.0020 g) were placed in a GenLab prime air circulating oven and held isothermally at 250 °C. Measurements of the samples' masses were recorded on a weekly basis.

2.5 Moisture uptake

Moisture uptake measurements were performed on cured resins of dimensions 2 mm x 12 mm x 35 mm, using a Vötsch Industrietechnik VC 7034 moisture chamber. Conditions of 85 % RH at 80 °C were used, as dictated by the ASTM Standard [17]. Measurements of the samples' masses were recorded periodically, initially at short interval time periods for the first four days, followed by twice-weekly measurements.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The cured resins based on binary [1_x:2_y] blends produced transparent, dark brown solids, and Koh *et al.* attributed the colour to thermal oxidation of the resin [18]. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was employed to establish the curing behaviour of the binary blends, dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) to determine their glass transition temperature (T_g), and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) to determine their thermal stability under inert atmosphere. Through DSC analysis, the presence of single, bell shaped curves in the DSC thermograms of all blends confirm the simultaneous reaction of the components of the blends. Throughout the blends, the values of the onset of polymerisation (T_o), the temperature of the exothermic peak maximum (T_{exo}), and the value of the polymerisation enthalpy (ΔH_c) remained relatively constant, indicating that there is little or no effect on the reaction of the two cyanate esters by altering their stoichiometry. However, an increase in both T_o and T_{exo} (30 and 15 °C respectively), as well as a decrease in ΔH_c is evident when compared to PT-30 (1), which is attributed to the complexity of the reaction, introduced by both the homopolymerisation reaction and the slower copolymerisation (arising from the lower reactivity of the LECy component).

Using DMA, the analysis of the cured sample of PT-30 displays a T_g (α transition) at 410 °C, based on the tan delta peak, a subtle β transition at 220 °C, and a modest γ transition at 95 °C. The binary blend $1_{85}:2_{15}$ was chosen for a comparative study, displaying a slightly higher storage modulus than the PT-30 reference. The profile of the tan delta response is similar, with a β transition also falling at 220 °C. The drop in the storage modulus, heralding the start of the T_g , commences slightly earlier than PT-30 (at 300 °C), but reaches a peak maximum at a similar temperature.

Using TGA it was observed that all of the blends show similar thermal stability up to initial mass loss of 5 wt%; the binary blends [$1_x:2_y$] containing at least 75 wt% PT-30 (**1**), are comparable with PT-30 (**1**) homopolymer up to a mass loss of 10 wt% (although other differences probably fall within the experimental error of the technique), but only the binary blends containing at least 85 wt% PT-30 (**1**) offer thermal stability of a similar order at mass losses of 20 wt %.

3.1 Examining the processability of the binary blends

Resin processing techniques, such as resin transfer moulding (RTM), vacuum assisted resin injection moulding (VARIM), or wet filament winding (FW) require viscosities of 100-1000 mPa.s at the lowest possible temperature [19]. Higher viscosities result in non-uniform wetting, possible void formation, and poor mechanical properties in the cured laminate. Consequently, a low viscosity dicyanate ester monomer, derived from bisphenol E (**2**), was used as a reactive diluent to the more viscous phenolic triazine oligomer (**1**), as a means of achieving a lower viscosity prepolymer, which simplifies the manufacturing process and enables the resin to be more versatile in terms of its processing.

The benchmark material used in this study (**1**) is a high performance, cyanated novolac with a viscosity of 296 Pa.s at 30 °C in the uncured polymer. LECy (**2**) is a waxy monomer (a supercooled liquid), which remains molten when heated, until crystallites develop in the system, at which point it solidifies. The incorporation of LECy was tested at several compositions varying from [$1_{100}:2_0$] to [$1_{75}:2_{25}$]. Incorporation of LECy (**2**) resulted in a significant reduction in the viscosity of the binary blend: a two-fold drop in viscosity was achieved by addition of 5 wt% of LECy in [$1_{95}:2_5$] (149 Pa.s), while at 25 wt%, the viscosity dropped down to 9.6 Pa.s in [$1_{75}:2_{25}$] (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Semi-Log of complex viscosity against temperature plot of binary [$1_x:2_y$] blends.

The processing temperatures were reduced by more than 10 °C *via* the incorporation of 15 wt% of LECy, resulting in a more simplified and cost-effective process (Table 2).

System	Complex viscosity (Pa.s) at 30 °C	Temperature at which complex viscosity reaches 1000 mPa.s (°C)
1	296	72
2	$8 \cdot 10^{-2}$	< 20
1₉₅:2₅	149	68
1₉₀:2₁₀	89	65
1₈₅:2₁₅	37	59
1₈₀:2₂₀	17	54
1₇₅:2₂₅	10	52

Table 2: A list of viscosity values at room temperature and minimum temperature at which liquid resin processing is possible

3.2 Thermo-oxidative stability of cured resin blends

While the behaviour in nitrogen (TGA) is informative, the application would see the materials exposed at elevated temperatures in air. All cured binary blends were exposed to more demanding conditions as their thermo-oxidative stability was assessed in air during isothermal exposure at 250 °C over an extended period of exposure (3048 hours) (Fig. 2). The homopolymer of Primaset™ PT-30 (**1**) was included as the baseline, and the cured commercial polycyanurate loses 45 % of its mass after a period of 3048 hours' exposure. Of the binary blends, [**1₉₅:2₅**], containing the greatest amount of PT-30 (**1**), predictably displays a similar level of performance (48 % loss), but even when higher levels of LECy (**2**) are incorporated, similar levels of stability can be achieved up to periods of 400 hours.

Figure 2: Thermo-oxidative stability for PT-30 (**1**) and binary **1_x:2_y** blends when exposed in air at 250 °C.

3.3 Determination of moisture uptake in cured resin blends

Cured resin plaques for selected samples (PT-30 (**1**) and **1**₈₀:**2**₂₀) were exposed to conditions of high temperature and high humidity (80 °C and 85% RH) for an extended period of time (3127 hours). Whilst the moisture absorption profiles do not reach equilibrium for these 2 mm thick samples, the plots suggest that a plateau is beginning to form (Fig. 3). The initial region of the absorption curves was found to be linear, characteristic of Fickian diffusion, and after the initial rapid uptake, the absorption process was comparatively slow. Of the two samples tested, Primaset™ PT-30 is the poorest performing, reaching a mass increase of over 5.2 wt% under these conditions. The introduction of the Primaset™ LECy (**2**) component with the more hydrophobic ethylidene moiety reduces the moisture uptake significantly (a drop of around 0.3 wt%). Jones *et al.* [20] performed an extensive study of the moisture uptake characteristics of cyanate-epoxy copolymers and reported that one of the more important factors which determines the concentration of moisture that a polymer will absorb is the effect of non-random mixing, whereby water-clustering is said to occur. In their studies, with complementary relative humidity of 40% and higher, the cluster size indicated that the majority of the water in a cured cyanate ester/epoxy blend is not clustered, but is present as a monomeric form, presumably hydrogen bonded to polar sites. Although the epoxy-containing networks will be more polar than either the Primaset™ PT-30 homopolymer or the binary blend examined here, the same observations are relevant since a reduction in the number of hydrogen bonding sites results in a reduction in moisture absorption.

Figure 3: Moisture absorption profiles for PT-30 (**1**) (red) and selected a binary blend **1**₈₅:**2**₁₅ when exposed to 80 °C, 85 % RH.

Previous work by Crawford *et al.* to examine binary blends of cyanate ester resins [21] investigated the influence of network crosslink density and the tortuosity of the path on moisture ingress and egress, and the resulting degradation mechanisms. They postulated that the formation of a more open, less crosslinked polycyanurate network might be responsible for the more rapid ingress and egress of moisture, leading to reduced moisture uptake.

4 CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown here that the processing characteristics of a commercial phenolic-triazine (PT) resin can be improved significantly through the addition of relatively small quantities of a commercial low viscosity difunctional cyanate ester to achieve reactive binary systems. Throughout this work, the properties of the blends are compared against an industrial standard (Primaset™ PT-30). It is found that blends containing 20-25 wt% LECy exhibit low viscosities (<1000 mPa.s) at 50 °C, making them suitable for liquid composite moulding processes. Dynamic differential scanning calorimetry confirmed the simultaneous reaction of the components of the blends and indicated that there is little or no effect on the reaction of the two cyanate esters by altering their stoichiometry. The thermomechanical performances of the cured blends compare favourably with the industrial standard system (Primaset™ PT-30), with the best performing systems exhibiting T_g values in excess of 300 °C based on the drop in storage modulus (compared with value of at least 350 °C for PT-30). After conditioning for 3127 hours at 80 °C and 85% RH, a cured binary resin blend absorbed 4.9 wt% of moisture, compared with a figure of 5.2 wt% for Primaset™ PT-30. When exposed to 250 °C in air continuously over a period of 3048 hours, the best performing of the binary cured blends lose 48 % of their mass, compared with 45 % for Primaset™ PT-30 under the same conditions. The significant advances made here in improving the resin blends' processability open the door for their use in manufacture of fibre reinforced composites by liquid moulding techniques for the first time. The processability of the new resin blends and the mechanical properties of the resulting composites will be the subject of future studies.

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